

EFFECT OF DOLOMITE MINERAL ON SURFACE ROUGHNESS OF HIGH DENSITY FIBERBOARD (HDF)

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to determine surface roughness properties of high density fiberboard (HDF) manufactured adding dolomite mineral which have fire retardant effects. Dolomite mineral were added into the fibers made from %50 scots pine (*pinus sylvestris L.*) and 50% beech (*Fagus orientalis Lipsky*) woods at 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% levels based on oven-dry fiber weight, respectively. HDF panels were produced in 6.5 mm thickness. The surface roughness of the obtained panels was measured by Marsurf M300 apparatus. Three roughness parameters, namely average roughness (R_a), mean peak-to-valley height (R_z), and maximum roughness (R_{max}) were determined from the surface of the samples. Results showed that roughness values of the samples increased with increasing dolomite mineral concentration used in panels manufacturing.

Keywords: HDF, dolomite, surface roughness

YÜKSEK YOĞUNLUKLU LİFLEVHANIN (HDF) YÜZEY PÜRÜZLÜLÜĞÜ ÜZERİNE DOLOMİT MİNERALİNİN ETKİSİ

Özet Bu çalışmanın amacı yanmayı geciktirici etkiye sahip dolomit mineralinin eklenmesi ile yüksek yoğunluklu liflevhanın yüzey pürüzlülüğü üzerine etkisini araştırmaktır. Dolomit minerali tam kuru lif ağırlığına göre %5,10,15,20 ve 25 oranlarında %50 sarıçam ve %50 kayın lifleri arasına eklenerek karıştırılmıştır. 6.5 mm kalınlığında yüksek yoğunluklu liflevha (HDF) elde edilmiştir. Eldedeilen levhalarda Marsurf M300 cihazı ile yüzey pürüzlülüğü ölçülmüştür. Üç yüzey pürüzlülüğü parametresi (R_a , R_z , ve R_{max}) değerleri belirlenmiştir. Elde edilen sonuçlara göre panel üretiminde dolomite mineralinin kullanım oranının artması ile yüzey pürüzlülüğünde artışı belirlenmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: HDF, dolomit, yüzey pürüzlülüğü

1 Introduction

Medium density fiberboard (MDF) is one of the most commonly used wood-based panels that is composed of wood fibers bonded together with interior adhesive under heat and pressure (1). In recent years production of MDF has significantly increased and has major market share in wood composites industry. Medium density fiberboard has many advantages such as smoother surface, easier machinability, and being ideal panel material as substrate for thin overlays used indoor conditions. However MDF also has some drawbacks similar the other wood-based panels such as poor fire retardant properties, low resistance against biological deterioration by fungi and termite. Wood and wood-based materials are composed of carbon and hydrogen components; therefore, when the temperature reaches about 275°C, combustion behavior is observed (2). This event is life threatening in public places. In order to reduce flammability and provide safety, wood is treated with fire-retardant chemicals (3). Therefore, it is important to control such disadvantages to improve efficient

use of wood-based panels as HDF. Boric acid and borax are largely used in the wood protection industry (4). It is known that dolomite mineral are used to enhance some properties of wood-based panels as fire retardant. In addition, dolomite (DOL) is mineral used as a fire retardant in certain applications. Dolomite is a type of calcium magnesium carbonate ($CaCO_3 \cdot MgCO_3$) that is widely available in nature (5). However boron compounds and dolomite mineral also have some adverse effect on the mechanical and physical properties of HDF and the other wood-based panels (6).

Roughness is a measure of the fine irregularities on a surface. The height width and shape of their regularities establish the surface quality of a product. Medium density fiberboard has smoother surface than that of any other interior wood composite panels. The surface roughness is important when MDF is used as substrate for overlays affecting product grades quality, finishing and gluing. Some of the parameters influencing the degree of surface roughness include manufacturing process and raw material characteristics. There are several methods which can be employed to determine

surface roughness of wood composites [7]. One of them is stylus method that is widely used in plastics and metal industries. It is practical, accurate and repeatable method [8]. Currently there is no detailed study with evaluate surface characteristics of experimentally manufactured HDF panels treated with dolomite mineral. Therefore, the objective of this study is to determine influence of dolomite mineral used in HDF panels on their surface characteristics.

2 Methodology

2.1 Raw Materials

Wood fibers (a 50:50 blend) consisting of pine and beech species were obtained from a commercial MDF plant, SFC

Integrated Wood Company, in Gebze, Turkey. The moisture content of the fibers, as determined by oven-dry weight, was found to be 3% to 4% prior to treatment. Dolomite mineral fire retardants used in the treatments was obtained from Doltaş Chemical Company, İzmir, Turkey. The powdered dolomite mineral was then added to the blender at target contents of 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% based on the oven-dry fiber weight. A commercial liquid UF resin, with a 55%solid content and a specific gravity of 1.23 was used.

Table 1. Dolomite Mineral

Chemical composition	CaMg(CO ₃) ₂
Crystal system	Hegzagonal
Hardness (Shore D)	3.5-4
Specific gravity	2.86
Opacity (%)	98
Weight Loss (1000 °C) (gr)	47.57

Table 2. Chemical composition of Dolomite (%)

CaO	31.10
MgO	21.04
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.03
SiO ₂	0.22
Al ₂ O ₃	0.02
Na ₂ O	<0.01
K ₂ O	<0.01

2.2 Panel Manufacturing

Dolomite mineral was added homogeneously in ratios of 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% within glued fibers, and then they were mixed. Density profiles of HDF panels produced using 300x300x100 mm size cold-pressing were checked via GreCon™ device. The panels were pressed under 3.5 MPa

pressure applied over the panels in a Cemil Usta SSP 125 press machine. Thickness was set at 8 mm by using thickness wedges. Using rubbing, 980–1000 kg/m³ density HDF panels were cut to 6.5±2 mm thick. Production conditions for the HDF panel are displayed in Table 3. HDF panels were conditioned at 20 °C of temperature and 65% relative humidity for three weeks before initial surface roughness evaluations were carried out.

Table 3. Hot Pressing Parameters for HDF Production

Parameters	
Temperature (°C)	183
Press (MPa)	3.5
Time (s)	18

2.3 Determination of surface roughness

Ten 100 mm 100 mm surface roughness test samples were cut from each panel. One measurement was performed on each surface roughness test sample across the grain orientation of the top HDF. A total of 40 roughness measurements of the surface of each type of treated samples and control samples were taken using a stylus type profilometer, Marsurf M300 (Fig. 1). Tracing speed, stylus tip diameter, and tip angle were 10

mm/min, 4 mm and 90, respectively. Fifteen millimeter tracing length (Lt) with 2.5 mm cut-off was used for the measurements. The measuring force of the scanning arm on the surfaces was 4 mN (0.4 g) which did not put any significant damage on the surface [9]. Measurements were repeated whenever the stylus tip fell into the cell lumen for several times during the tests. The calibration of the instruments was checked every 100 measurements by using a standard reference plate with Ra values of 3.02 and 0.40 μm. Fig. 1 illustrates a typical roughness

profile for an untreated control and for HDF samples treated with 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% of dolomite mineral. Three roughness parameters, mean arithmetic deviation of profile (R_a), mean peak-to-valley height (R_z), and maximum roughness (R_{max}) were commonly used in previous studies to evaluate surface characteristics of wood and wood composites including HDF [10]. R_a is the average distance from the profile to the mean line over the length of assessment. R_z can be calculated from the peak-to-valley values of five equal lengths within the

profile while maximum roughness (R_{max}) is the distance between peak and valley points of the profile which can be used as an indicator of the maximum defect height within the assessed profile [11]. Therefore, such parameters which are characterized by ISO 4287 [12] were also employed to evaluate influence of chemical treatment on the surface roughness of HDF specimens. The specifications of these parameters are described in details in various works [13].

Fig. 1. Outline of the stylus type profilometer— Marsurf M300

3 Findings

Table 4 and Fig. 2 show results of average surface roughness parameters of the panels.

Table 4. Average surface roughness parameters (R_a , R_z and R_{max}) of the panels

Dolomite Ratio (%)	$R_a(\mu\text{m})$	$R_z(\mu\text{m})$	$R_{max}(\mu\text{m})$
5	6.46 (0.95)*	39.31 (5.47)	51.03 (5.89)
10	6.62 (0.36)	42.17 (6.57)	53.45 (3.78)
15	6.79 (0.90)	43.00 (2.94)	54.82 (5.50)
20	7.01 (0.47)	43.87 (3.03)	55.45 (6.93)
25	7.33 (0.58)	46.56 (6.01)	57.51 (7.08)
Control	4.24 (0.46)	28.68 (2.88)	38.85 (5.01)

*Numbers in parentheses are standard deviations

Fig. 2. Average values of R_a , R_z and R_{max} parameters.

3.1 Average surface roughness (R_a)

R_a values of all treated samples showed a difference as compared to untreated sample, as shown in Table 1. The treated specimens had higher average surface roughness than that of untreated samples. The R_a values for the 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% levels of dolomite mineral with treated panels are always rougher than the control panel samples. These samples had also the smoothest surface of any treated specimens with $6.46\mu\text{m}$ R_a . As concentration of dolomite, average R_a values also increased. Increased concentration of dolomite mineral also adversely influenced surface quality of the samples. Samples treated with 25% concentration of dolomite mineral had the roughest surface with R_a value of $7.33\mu\text{m}$. Samples treated with 25% concentration of dolomite mineral resulted in rougher surface with R_a than those of treated with 5%.

3.2 Mean peak-to-valley values (R_z)

The R_z value of untreated samples had the lowest value among the treated. It was determined a significant difference among the treatment groups. Samples treated with 25% concentration of dolomite mineral had the highest R_z value of $46.56\mu\text{m}$. In relation to the increase in the ratios of dolomite mineral, an increase in surface roughness occurred. In comparison to the control sample, in the 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% concentrations, R_z values of samples were found 39.31, 42.17, 43.00, 43.87, and $46.56\mu\text{m}$ respectively (Table 4).

3.3 Maximum roughness values (R_{max})

The R_{max} values of all treated samples were higher than that of untreated sample. R_{max} values of the treated samples are dramatically different to the untreated control sample. Samples treated with 25% concentration of dolomite mineral had the highest R_{max} value of $57.51\mu\text{m}$ like R_a and R_z . Increased concentration of dolomite mineral adversely influenced R_{max} values of the samples. In comparison to the control sample, in the 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% concentrations, the R_{max} value of samples were found 51.03, 53.45, 54.82, 55.45, and $57.51\mu\text{m}$ respectively. The R_{max} value of the samples with treated dolomite mineral increased with increasing dolomite mineral concentration as shown in Table 4.

4 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study evaluated surface roughness of HDF treated with dolomite mineral. Three roughness parameters could be used as an indicator to quantify the surface characteristics of the treated samples. It was found that such parameters are able to differentiate the surface roughness of the panels due to different concentration levels. All of the treatments adversely affected surface roughness of the panels. The negative influence of dolomite mineral on the surface roughness was 25% ratio the highest among concentrations used for the treatment dolomite mineral.

However, this study indicates that surface roughness of the panels can be adversely influenced by increased concentrations of dolomite mineral. Therefore, chemical concentration should be carefully adjusted to provide sufficient dolomite mineral as fire retardant for treated HDF while also providing minimal negative effects on its surface roughness. Further studies performed to use treatment of the panels should evaluate the less intervals of chemicals to attain a better understanding of the effect of treatment variables on the surface quality of the panels. Also other roughness parameters such as maximum valley height and core roughness can be included to have detailed information about the treated surfaces.

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